

Our approach has been to work from the bottom-up, addressing the foundational communications architecture first. We saw this aspect to FVI crucial to the success of the other features. As there was very little science to support a security model that accounted for the dynamic need to share information that is prevalent in many situations that the military finds itself, we started there.

One of the first results our group achieved was a set of extensions to the Bell-LaPadula model. We summarize our results here, but a complete discussion is found in [1].

Many of the available solutions for sharing information have successfully created multi-level secure systems (networks of systems) which follow access control rules (many based on the Bell-LaPadula security model) in which access to information is granted to a given level of classified information once confirmation is achieved that a given subject has the required clearance (mandatory access control). However, the current implementation of mandatory access controls and role-based access controls does not support mission success for those missions that require sharing information on an ad hoc basis, especially at the lowest tactical level for operations which require social and cultural awareness of local populations and NGOs as well as local support in achieving mission success.

Hence, we extended the Bell-LaPadula model to include continuous and discrete system states as is done for current general system theory for control of complex, distributed systems. We also extended the Bell-LaPadula definitions for "security" and "compromise" to include a definition of a "need-to-share" and a "failure to share". A basic result concerning security in computer systems, using the precise notions for "security", "compromise", "sharing", "need-to-know", and "need-to-share" was then provided.

These extensions laid the groundwork for building more accurate models of the complex operational environments of today and tomorrow. Additionally, they provided the foundation for providing automation support for a commander's decision to share information while simultaneously maintaining the security of information which must not be compromised. We then applied general systems theory to prove that a computer system with its data protected under a "need-to-know" policy could securely coexist with data managed with a "need-to-share" policy.

III. RELATED WORK

There has been a lot of interest lately in efficient means for sharing information. In [2], the authors present a taxonomy of influences on intelligence information sharing that includes consideration of technical, legal and social elements. Our work is focused on addressing the technical barriers that they described. Several models assume or require a more permanent network architecture, e.g. [3], [4], [5] and [6]. Our approach is specifically designed for ad hoc, non-permanent networks. In addition, our approach enables fine-grained sharing of information in accordance with information sharing policy decisions made by the owners of the information (i.e. for military operations, unit commanders are the "owners" of information describing details of unit operations).

In [7] the authors present a taxonomy of Mobile Ad hoc Networks (MANETs). They separate them into two general categories: fully self-organized and authority based. FVI-NTS falls into the second category dividing their authority into two entities—authority and master base trust certifier (discussed below)—which enables secure and obscured transmission of data between nodes. There has been much work at securing the transmission layer protocols, e.g. [8], [9], [10] and [11]. Our effort is focused at the application layer and assumes that lower layers are secured.

IV. THE FVI-NTS ARCHITECTURE

The FVI-NTS node architecture (Figure 2) is an implementation of the formal results described in section II,

Figure 2. FVI-NTS cloud and attached networks.

above. It is an approach to provide automation support for a commander's decision to share information with other organizations that may not be on the secure military network. The FVI-NTS solution does not alter any existing information security controls based on established "need to know" policies for maintaining information security. It should be noted that this architecture is specifically designed for information sharing in ad hoc networks.

A. Design philosophy

There are several assumptions and decisions that form our design philosophy. We list them here to provide a common foundation.

First, the FVI-NTS architecture makes no assumptions about the process results in a decision to share information by a local organization. This is outside the FVI-NTS system boundary.

Second, trust between the authorities that are the representatives for their respective organizations on the NTS group is the basis for sharing. No assumption about the actual distribution of information at the other end of a need to share relationship is 'enforced' by this software.

Next, how and with whom a receiving authority chooses to share contents from another organization is also not dictated by the system's design. Agreement between authorities may result in ways of designating the parties in the receiving

organization information is intended for [additional files might be provided in the set of files being transmitted].

It should also be noted that the NTS design is not intended as a support for systems that require a “dynamic” response relationship. The nature of the file sets being exchanged is static. A session-based communications protocol, such as the Common Object Request Broker Architecture (CORBA), would not be appropriate in this design. Because the parties involved often do not have continuous, predictable network support, the design provides for allowing graceful operation and the ability to “catch-up” with operational results that occurred when a system experienced some network interruption.

Only the ‘local’ authority for each node accesses a node. Between the nodes, regular RSYNC executions occur that keep each sending-nodes’ locally generated content files available on the other nodes. The actual transmission of content from the ‘sending’ node to the other nodes is controlled by the execution of RSYNC from a ‘receiving’ node

Finally, any complete replacement of the set of files associated with an individual transaction will be detected by the failure to decrypt the individual authority key for the ZIP file or the signature value also included with the encrypted symmetric key will not match the locally computed signature for the ZIP file.

B. Node communications protocol

The FVI-NTS system follows a 5-step protocol for sharing information among clients in the cloud. These steps are *request*, *aggregation*, *transport*, *decomposition*, and *consumption*. We will describe the FVI-NTS architecture in terms of these five steps.

1) Request

When a user in an organization desires to share information (Figure 3), such as documents, media, data, etc, she must submit it to the organization’s ‘Authority’ that analyzes the information and either approves or rejects the request. The ‘Authority’ (Figure 3) can be a person or an automated system. We make no assumptions and consider this part of the protocol outside the responsibility of FVI-NTS.

Figure 3. A user requesting to share information.

2) Aggregation

When an outgoing set of files has been reviewed and accepted for sharing by the ‘sending’ organization’s authority, the data is aggregated in preparation for transport (Figure 4). There are six sub-steps in the FVI-NTS protocol that accomplish this task.

1. The set of files to sent are compressed (including any relative sub-paths) into a ZIP file.
2. The ZIP file is encrypted with a randomly generated symmetric key.
3. For each node that files are being shared with, the symmetric key (generated in step 2) and the digest signature of the encrypted ZIP files are encrypted with the public key for the receiving authority. The file is then saved with the encrypted ZIP file (from step 2). The name of the encrypted key file is that of the node being “shared to.” An encrypted key file is also generated for sending node (with its name).
4. For each node that is not being shared with, an encrypted key file is written but the symmetric key value used is zero (which never occurs otherwise). The set of files to be sent are compressed (including any relative sub-paths) into a ZIP file.
5. The set of encrypted key files and the ZIP files are saved to a directory named initially “Txxxxxxxxxxxxx” where xxxxxxxxxxxxxxxx is replaced with the millisecond accurate clock on the authority’s workstation.
6. After all the files have been copied to the local node, the directory is renamed with the initial “T” removed. [Note: only new directories without an initial ‘T’ are processed by receiving NTS authority workstations. Should an RSYNC capture a directory that has not been ‘finalized’ it will not be processed until a subsequent RSYNC occurs and renames the directory.]

Figure 4. Authority workstation preparing documents to share.

Authority' can be a person or an automated system. We make not assumptions and consider this part of the protocol outside the responsibility of FVI-NTS.

3) Transport

After the files have been collected and encrypted, the authority the moves the set of files to the local node (Figure 5). At that point, the data is copied to the other nodes in the cloud.

Figure 5. The Authority moves the collected files to the local NTS node.

Each local node will have a directory of directories that include the sets of sets¹ of files to be shared with other members of the NTS group of organizations. RSYNC will only copy new content to other nodes. All content on each node is encrypted. Each node has the needed keys to run RSYNC (within a SSH tunnel session) on each of the other nodes. No authority's private or public keys are ever stored on a node. Should a node's file contents ever become accessible to anyone outside the group of authorities participating in the 'need to share' group the content will remain 'secure' from inappropriate access.

4) Decomposition

At receiving end of the node cloud architecture, the tasks are the same, but simply reversed. The node authority will move the interested zip file (or files) off the node onto the local network.

5) Consumption

On the local network, the authority will use his public key to decrypt the ZIP file and proper disperse the files within his/her organization.

Central to this design is the existence of a party acting as the Master Basic Trust Certifier (MBTC) that provides the access certificates on each node for the other nodes (thus allowing SSH-RSYNCH based communication). The MBTC also communicates the public keys of the authorities to each of

¹ This is not a typographical error. We refer to sets of files within other files such as folders within folders.

the other authorities. The individual authorities for each organization can use OPENSSEL software to generate their public and private keys. The MBTC does need to know the public or private keys of any of the authority workstations. What encrypted content the members choose to move is obscured from the view of the MBTC. A specific MBTC can provide the management of the NTS group of nodes without ever having access to the actual content being transmitted.

It should be noted that this architecture provides a solution to the *end node problem*, where an un-trusted, individual computer becomes part of a trusted, network. The data that is stored on each node is encrypted and essentially inaccessible to any node except for the intended receiver. As a result, there is no issue with a need to trust. Any computer that joins the FVI-NTS cloud, however, must first obtain the proper keys from the MBTC.

V. SECURITY

We now discuss the security aspects that have been designed into the FVI-NTS architecture. We will explain them in terms in terms of authentication, authorization, integrity, confidentiality and non-repudiation.

A. Authentication

The authority workstation operator is the principal individual of concern in NTS operations. He has access to a specific authority's private key which is needed to digitally sign content being approved for "need to share" from the authority's organization to select NTS member organizations. Movement of content between NTS nodes uses credentials loaded on the node by the MBTC. This data does not provide the information needed to decrypt any of the content being shared.

B. Authorization

What a specific NTS authority is limited to in the operations associated with the local NTS node is set by the design of NTD. What the authority workstation can access on internal files systems is outside any operational impact of NTS.

C. Integrity

The design of NTS provides for detection of any attempt to modify content after it leaves the authority workstation that provided the content to be shared. The encrypted ZIP file of the files being shared has a signature and symmetric session key provided to each organization's authority. Each receiving authority has the public key from the signing authority. This provides the means to computationally assert the integrity of the received transmission.

D. Confidentiality

This security aspect is addressed by the use of encryption of the actual data as well as the signature for the content by the originator. A symmetric key and cryptographic key are generated for every set of files being shared.

E. Non-repudiation

The present design provides for non-repudiation by the sender because only the sharing authority can sign the content (using the authority's private key). No specific provision

directly provides a secure confirmation of the receipt of the content by the designated recipients. If this functionality is needed, the receiving authority can simply “package” the transactional name of set of files received (after the receiving authority has distributed the files internally in the receiving organization) and “share” this information for response to the sending node and authority.

VI. FUTURE WORK

After extensive local testing, we plan to apply FVI-NTS in an operational environment using mission related data to demonstrate its capability to be used as a cross domain solution for information sharing. Our intent is to leverage our relationship with the National Military Academy of Afghanistan (NMAA) to move more sensitive but unclassified data between USMA and NMAA.

We are also currently working on applying FVIT-NTS with other network edge devices. We are initially using Android smart phones in conjunction with tactical robots as a proof of concept demonstration.

Finally, we are planning to develop a real-time extension called FVI-NTS-RT (real time). Using a multicast protocol, the goal will be to share streaming data, such as videos, in addition to static data.

VII. CONCLUSION

In this work, we have presented an overview of the Flowing Valued Information-Need-To-Share project and the problem domain it addresses. Additionally, we discussed our approach and described the FVI-NTS system architecture as well as future directions.

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